

COTTAGE CHEESE PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

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Cottage cheese is a protein solid product. Cottage cheese is made from skim or skim milk. To do this, the milk is fermented with pure milk-yogurt bacteria or enzyme preparations (juice or pepsin) are added. The resulting curd is pressed and the whey is squeezed out of it: then the cottage cheese is cooled to a temperature of 8-10 C and placed in barrels. Cottage cheese is one of the most nutritious foods. It has healing properties and contains 14-17% protein, up to 18% fat, 2.4-2.8% milk sugar, calcium, phosphorus, iron and magnesium.

Depending on the fat content, cottage cheese is high in fat - up to 18%, low in fat - up to 9% and defatted. The quality of cottage cheese is divided into excellent and 1st grade. The high-quality cottage cheese has an elegant consistency, is slightly yellow, white in color and has a clean and pleasant milky-yogurt taste. In 1st grade cottage cheese, the taste of the food and the filling is slightly noticeable, slightly crumbly and sticky.

The nutritional value of cottage cheese is due to its high content of essential amino acids, especially methionine, mezin and chomen.

Homen with methionine normalizes liver function. Methionine helps the body get rid of cholesterol. Homen is necessary for the normal functioning of the nervous system. Cottage cheese contains a lot of minerals (calcium, phosphorus, iron, magnesium, etc.), which have a positive effect on tissue structure and bone formation.

Children especially need cottage cheese. Because calcium and phosphorus are used in the formation of bone tissue and blood. Cottage cheese is also prescribed for people with tuberculosis, anemia, rickets. Consumption of cottage cheese and cottage cheese products helps to maintain a normal metabolism and maintain a certain level of osmotic pressure. Cottage cheese increases the excretion of water from the body, it is recommended to consume cottage cheese in case of edema, eczema, hypertension and others.

Cottage cheese can be produced in two ways. These are: traditional and separation methods.

There are two types of cottage cheese that can be made in the traditional way, depending on the condition of the curd.

These are: acidic cottage cheese and acidic cottage cheese.

In the production of acidic cottage cheese, the resulting mixture is heated to accelerate the separation of whey. Cottage cheese made in this way has little or no fat, because when heated, a large amount of fat in the curd passes into the whey. Such cottage cheese is a diet cottage cheese.

Acid-sour curd is made by adding lactic acid bacteria and whey enzymes to the milk, and after the protein is fermented, the whey is separated. In this case, the action of the enzyme syrup results in the formation of casein-paracasein in the first stage of milk protein digestion, and in the second stage from the paracasein. Casein raises the pH-isoelectric point from 4.6 to 5.2 during the transition to paracasein.

Therefore, the process of making cottage cheese in this method is carried out in a low acidic environment and 2-4 hours before the process of making acidic cottage cheese. The protein structure of the sludge, which is formed in the production of acid-curd cottage cheese, combines quickly and there is no need to heat the slag. This method allows you to make high-fat and medium-fat cottage cheese, because the amount of fat does not pass into the whey due to lack of heat treatment. Another advantage of this method is that in the preparation of acidic cottage cheese, the calcium salts in it are transferred to the whey by heating, while in the preparation of acidic cottage cheese, these salts are retained in the sediment. The raw material is high-quality fresh skim milk and pure milk with an acidity of 20 T. Normalized and purified milk is pasteurized at a temperature of 78-80 C for 20-30 seconds. Pasteurized milk is cooled to a temperature of 28-

30 C, and for the production of cottage cheese, the product is sent to the baths, and for fermentation, 1-5% of milk is added dropwise and left to ferment for 6-8 hours.

In the process of making sour-cream cottage cheese, a drop of milk is added to a solution of 40% calcium chloride. (400 g per 1 ton of milk). Calcium chloride helps pasteurized milk to form a solid and whey-forming precipitate using the enzyme enzyme. After the addition of calcium chloride, a 1% solution of boiled enzymes or pepsin is added to the milk, which is boiled and cooled to a temperature of 35 C. In order to remove the remaining whey from the sediment, it is sent to the resin or simply pressed. To do this, 7-9 kg of sediment is packed in bags, sealed and placed in several rows on a press cart. Due to its weight, the sediment is pressed and the whey is released. Self-pressing is carried out for 1 hour in rooms with a temperature of 160 C. The cottage cheese is then pressed under pressure until ready. This pressing is carried out in a building at 3-6 C, and after the process the cheese is quickly sent to the refrigerator to cool to a temperature of 80 C.

Production of cottage cheese using the method of separation. First, the milk is heated to a temperature of 40-45 C in a plate apparatus, and the cream is obtained in a separator until 50-55% fat remains. The cream is pasteurized in a plate device at a temperature of 90 aC, cooled to a temperature of 2-4 C and sent for storage for some time. The skim milk is pasteurized at a temperature of 78-80 C for 20 seconds, cooled to a temperature of 30-34 C and sent to the tank for cooling. It contains calcium chloride and enzymes. The mixture is thoroughly mixed and brought to an acidity of 90-100 T. The resulting mixture is thoroughly mixed and sent by pump to a plate heat exchanger. The condensate is first heated to 60-62 C and then cooled to 28-32 C. As a result, the consistency is rapidly broken down into protein and whey components.

Under pressure, the condensate is transferred from the heat exchanger to the separator - the device for making cottage cheese, and is separated into cottage cheese. The curd obtained is cooled to a temperature of 8 C and matured until a homogeneous consistency is formed. The cooled cottage cheese is sent to a mixing machine, where it is thoroughly mixed with pasteurized, chilled cream by means of a pump.

Regular consumption of the product lowers blood cholesterol levels, strengthens the immune system. The miracle of fermented milk is able to protect the body's cells from cancerous tumors, including breast cancer. Cottage cheese grains are used for cosmetic purposes for the face. Consumption of cottage cheese is especially important for the elderly. As a person gets older, the bone tissue becomes very brittle. Cottage cheese is vital for pregnant women because the fetus in the uterus needs large amounts of easily digestible casein protein. Everyone's health is closely linked to proper nutrition, and cottage cheese is one of the most important healthy foods in this regard. Therefore, cottage cheese is important in the food industry.

References:

1. R.Khojiev Namangan Engineering-Pedagogical Institute, Department of Food Technology Methodical instructions for laboratory classes on the subject "Technology of milk and dairy products" Namangan 2005.
2. A.Karimkulov Gulistan State University, Department of Food Technology, Educational and Methodological Complex on Food Biotechnology Gulistan 2019.

Websites:

1. <https://uz.thomson-intermedia.com/how-to-look-for-lactose-free-food-887>.
2. www.zionet.uz.
3. www.biotex.com.